

Determine the Importance Level of Criteria in Creating Cultural Resources' Attractiveness from Tourists' Evaluation

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ABSTRACT

This study's goal is to present Solutions for Determining the importance level of criteria in creating cultural resources' attractiveness from tourists' evaluation. Data were collected from 558 international tourists who chose Vietnam as the destination for tourism.

The study points out that we need to resolve challenges such as: building a safe, friendly destination, etc., destinations need to review and re-evaluate the services of their products and tourist attractions to prepare for the largest number of visitors and stimulate the domestic tourism market is a good solution: To boost the domestic tourism market, it is necessary to increase domestic flights and train connections to major tourist destinations.

Keywords: Vietnam tourism; Challenges; Cultural attractiveness, Tourists' evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hoa Dinh Vu et al (2021) stated that demonstrate the severe impact of the pandemic on Vietnam's tourism industry based on a decrease in the number of visitors, business activities, revenue and employment rate.

The COVID-19 pandemic that first appeared in December 2019 in Wuhan, China, has affected more than 90% of the world's population and directly affected tourism businesses, restaurants, hotels, and airlines (Gössling, Scott & Hall, 2021).

(SOURCE: Internet)

Figure 1. Tea Hills in Thai Nguyen province

Stimulate domestic tourism market is good solution:

To boost the domestic tourism market, it is necessary to increase domestic flights and train connections to major

tourist destinations. This has both helped revive the Transport industry - the lifeblood of the economy and created conditions to promote the recovery of the domestic tourism industry.

Hence we select the topic: **Determine the importance level of criteria in creating cultural resources' attractiveness from tourists' evaluation**

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH MODEL

We see below table:

Table 1. Summary of related studies

Authors	Year	Contents, results
Kaplinsky and Morris	2011	Argue that “The value chain describes all the activities” needed to move a product or service through the various stages of production (involving a combination of material transformations and inputs into production services different), delivered to the final consumer, and disposed of after using.
Boudiaf	2019	Said that historical site preservation, esp. Historical buildings are important for cities preservation of culture.
Yucel	2020	For many years, Thailand and Malaysia have been two of the top 20 most visited countries globally.
Vu C. Thang	2020	While the global community is taking urgent measures to overcome difficulties for production and businesses and ensure social security in response to the Covid-19 pandemic, Vietnam tourism industry needs to develop policy measures to minimize economic recession. Based on the research documents of international development organizations on developing policy measures for socio-economic recovery and case studies in Asian countries when the pandemic outbreaks in the region and the world, we propose policy measures to manage Vietnam destination as a national tourism destination. Given the impacts by Covid-19 pandemic, the policy measures addressed in this paper are divided into 3 groups: (1) support businesses to minimize economic losses in order to best promote the tourism business models in pandemic situations; (2) promote tourism stimulus programs and public-private partnerships; and (3) restructure tourism businesses and proper business management models for a new normal situation, in line with sustainable development goals in the long-term.

(SOURCE: Author Synthesis)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data collection

The survey sample was selected through purposive sampling including international tourists (excluding overseas Vietnamese) who visiting Vietnam in different forms such as going through travel agencies or self-travel... and those who have come to visit cultural attractions in Vietnam. The survey was carried out in Hanoi, Da Nang, and Ho Chi Minh city, and also Tay Bac region which are the top three cities to welcome the most inbound international tourists and represent three cultural regions in Vietnam.

(SOURCE: Internet)

Figure 2. Ho Chi Minh city boost tourism

4. MAIN FINDINGS

4.1. Background data

The development of Vietnam's tourism industry is the result of the implementation of guidelines and policies of the Party and State, especially Resolution No. 08–NQ/TW dated January 16, 2017 of the Politburo on to develop tourism into a spearhead economic sector, with a goal that by 2020, the tourism industry will basically become a spearhead economic sector, creating a driving force for socio-economic development; has professionalism, has a relatively synchronous and modern system of material and technical foundations; tourism products of high quality, diversity, brand, imbued with national cultural identity, competitive with other countries in the region.

However, Vietnam's tourism still has some weaknesses in terms of tourism products, service quality, tourism environment, promotion and advertising, etc. Therefore, developing smart tourism will contribute to mitigate and overcome these weaknesses.

Beside, Leng Thi Lan, Dinh Tran Ngoc Huy, Nguyen Hang Phuong (2021) showed it can be said: the legend is the basis of arising and organizing the festival; The festival is the place to preserve and promote the value and vividly show the appearance and meaning of the legend. The case of legends and folk festivals in the territory of Thai Nguyen city is a vivid proof of that close-knit dialectical relationship. *For tourism, value chain approach can be considered as: A systematic approach from the public, communities to organize folk festivals till participants,*

tourists, local government and state management level with policies. We need to separate task division and labor division in tourism value chain.

(SOURCE: Vinpearl)

Figure 3. Tourism in Hoi An-Da Nang

(SOURCE: Internet)

Figure 4. Tourism in Vung Tau

(SOURCE: Internet)

Figure 5. Tourism in Dong Nai province

4.2. Evaluation criteria

The analysis results are presented below:

Chart 1: Importance level of criteria in creating cultural resources' attractiveness from tourists' evaluation

(SOURCE: Authors Analysis)

Look at above chart we see that:

- (i) First, the pleasant attitude of local people also has high corr of 0.629.
- (ii) Second, the uniqueness of cultural attraction also has high corr.

5. CONCLUSION

In general, we need to overcome challenges and take advantage of opportunities to boost tourism activities more in future.

(SOURCE: Internet)

Figure 6. Tour Thanh Hoa province of Vietnam

Finally we suggest some recommendations as:

First, we need to resolve challenges such as: build a safe, friendly destination..., destinations need to review and re-evaluate the services of their products and tourist attractions to prepare for the largest number of visitors, especially in the summer period. Control the selling price, security, order and safety for guests when visiting the resort, strengthen inspection of food hygiene and safety, etc.

Dinh Tran Ngoc Huy, Duong Thi Huyen, Nguyen Thu Thuy, Nguyen Thi Hang (2021) pointed that Ha Giang and Thai Nguyen are located in the Northern region of Vietnam, where have lots of potential historical and architecture sites for exploring and discover to boost community and cultural tourism. In specific, Thai Nguyen has now discovered more than 30 archaeological sites, concentrated mainly in the northern districts of the province such as Vo Nhai, Phu Luong, Dong Hy, Dai Tu. In which, Vo Nhai is the district with the most archaeological relics in Thai Nguyen province such as Hang Oc site, Than Sa site. In recent years, archaeological tourism activities in Vo Nhai have undergone many changes and achieved many important results.

Declarations

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The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Authors' Contributions

All authors equally contributed to research and paper drafting.

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